

Doctoral education during the pandemic and beyond: challenges and strategies

Thursday 26th August

15:45 – 16:45 CET

Abstract:

This session will discuss how the COVID-19 pandemic has affected early-career researchers and what lessons can be learned for doctoral education and training with a special focus on doctoral programmes in educational research related areas. Since the introduction of lockdowns throughout Europe during March 2020, many researchers have been forced to modify, restrict or reduce their research activity. Home working may suit some researchers but research work often depends on access to laboratories, research infrastructure, field work and archives. For those with parental responsibilities, the lockdown was accompanied by a closure of schools and childcare that reduced the time available to work from home. International researchers have experienced greater isolation. In particular, we will highlight issues related to the mental wellbeing of PhD candidates and discuss survey data showing how the crisis has exacerbated mental health issues among early-career researchers. This session will present and discuss strategies and practices from and for doctoral programs, including shifting PhD supervision, evaluation and promotions online, provision of online doctoral training, improving digital communication in doctoral supervision, securing doctoral funding extensions and handling restrictions in international mobility.

Extended Summary:

The COVID pandemic has had a huge impact on our societies and universities since March 2020. Doctoral candidates are the most junior level of academic researchers and have been more exposed to insecurity during the pandemic.

This session will depart from the currently available evidence of pitfalls in doctoral education and assessing the prevalence of mental health issues among early-career researchers before the pandemic. Often those most affected are those, who experience inequality, such as, younger researchers, female researchers, international researchers and those with caring responsibilities. The session will discuss the evidence of the prevalence of mental health issues among doctoral candidates, how COVID-19 exacerbated such mental health issues and discuss the effectiveness of interventions.

There will be a discussion of how existing EARLI research sheds light on a particular theme, or by considering new lines of research that need to be pursued.

During the session we will cover 4 important viewpoints:

1. Pre-Pandemic Assessment of Researcher Wellbeing. The emergence of lower levels of mental health among researchers predates the COVID pandemic. Inge van der Weijden is a leading researcher on the motivation, selection and evaluation of researchers in order to better understand their career development and to provide insight to policymakers and institutional stakeholders on higher education policy. She co-authored the report, *The Mental Well-Being of Leiden University PhD Candidates*, that proposed concrete measures for institutions to support the mental health of early-career researchers by:

- appointing independent psychologist for PhD candidates,
- establishing a supervision team for international PhD candidates,
- providing career coaching for both non-academic and academic careers,
- providing supervisor training for both new and experienced supervisors,
- providing transparency with regard to the requirements PhD candidates must meet,
- supporting independent PhD mentoring groups,
- frequently monitoring of the well-being of PhD candidates and
- evaluating chosen interventions.

2. Impact of COVID-19 Crisis on Researcher Wellbeing. We will examine the impact of the COVID-19 crisis on the research work, mental wellbeing and social connection of early-career researchers and research staff as evidenced by Janet Metcalfe's work as part of the SMARTEN/VITAE survey. This survey examined changes to employment outside of academia, living arrangements, caring arrangements and support by supervisors and by universities. The survey found that inequalities in research were a clear predictor of being more impacted by the COVID pandemic with females, caregivers, researchers with a physical disability or long-term illness and international researchers being more likely to be struggling with their mental wellbeing.

3. Digitization of the research environment. Although conferences, physical training courses and university lectures have been greatly restricted, there has been a strong increase in the uptake of digital transferable skills training during the last 12 months. Personalization of researcher training is not a novel discussion, however, the current COVID situation put this issue - together with the digitization of research environments - into the spotlight as well. Gábor Kismihók will contribute to the discussion from the point of view of learning and skills analytics, and showcase how to support early-career researchers in improving their career perspectives by assessing their skills gaps and recommending personalized training opportunities.

4. Institutional Adoption. Doctoral Programmes have adapted their programmes to meet the demands of COVID and the EUA Council of Doctoral Education has played a strong role supporting universities to make changes that will support the mental wellbeing of doctoral candidates. In particular, the EUA-CDE worked with European doctoral programmes in providing guidance and examples of good practice in response to the COVID-19 pandemic with regard to:

- Online assessment and doctoral dissertation defence
- Online skills training and supervision
- Supporting doctoral candidates' mental health and well-being
- The effect of the pandemic on collaborations and funding of doctoral education

In the aftermath of the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the mental wellbeing of doctoral candidates, this session suggests actions and practices that institutions can take not just to respond to this crisis but to improve the outcomes of doctoral education in general.

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